

The Effects of the Use of ICT as a Marketing Strategy on the Performance of SME: A Systematic Literature Review

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Abstract

This study seeks to investigate the effects of e-marketing both directly and indirectly on the performance of SMEs. The study is a systematic literature review conducted using meta-analysis. In the end, 24 articles comprised reports, conference papers, and journal articles were systematically reviewed with the intension of answering two research questions; what effects do e-marketing have on the return of SMEs? And Other than return, what other benefits does E-marketing have on SMEs? The research concluded that, e-marketing increases the return of the business by maximizing its sales and minimizing its cost. It further concluded that e-marketing helps in the growth of SMEs by increased its productivity and giving it a comparative advantage over its competitors and large firms.

Keywords: ICT, e-marketing, Marketing Performance and SMEs

1. INTRODUCTION

Marketing is the act of advertising or promoting the sales of goods (Aderemi, Ojediran, Adegbite, & Olasanmi, 2015). The main objective of a firm (mostly private company) is to make a profit. An organization can easily achieve that by making more sales. This makes marketing a vital function in a company. Irrespective of the fact that marketing is vital, not all organizations pay full attentions to their marketing department. Tiago M. and Tiago F. (2012) believed that concrete measures need to be taken by organizations in order to exploit their marketing potentials properly.

The definition of a Small and medium-sized enterprise (Futher-SME) varies from country to country. However, what is certain is that SMEs are very important to the economy (Taruté & Gatautis, 2014, El-Gohary, 2010). Dahnil, Marzuki, Langgat, & Fabeil, (2014) believed SMEs are the main contributors to economic development and employment. A study carried out by Kiveu M and Ofafa G (2013) in Kenya showed that according to GOK (2009), SMEs comprise 75% of all businesses, employs 30% of the population and accounts for 87% of Jobs. The importance of SMEs to the economy can never be fully comprehended or measured. Kiveu M and Ofafa G (2013) called it the “engine of growth”. The survival of SME is thus imperative. The concept of business has existed since the days of a trade by barter, where goods where exchanged for goods. One of the difficulties that existed using the barter system was the fact that you never knew who had what you needed. With the help of marketing, awareness is created on the different variety of commodities that exist thereby bring sellers and buyers closer. O'Donnell, (2013) defined marketing as “the process of identifying, communicating with and maintaining relationships with buyers of a producer's product to affect volume, value and timing sales directly”. Marketing is a precondition for the success of an enterprise, thus SME should fully utilize its marketing potentials in order to survive and grow. Thus marketing is imperative to SME

SME faces many challenges that hinder it from achieving its full potentials such as limited market access, poor market research and high cost of competition with large firms (Kiveu & Ofafa, 2013). However, with the evolution of technology, marketing is one of the highest business activity that has been affected by technological changes (Jayaram, Manrai, & Manrai, 2015), thus the evolution of marketing from the traditional system to digital marketing (e-marketing). Kiveu and Ofafa (2013) believed this evolution could be used to solve the problems being faced by SMEs. O'Donnell, (2013) supported this in a report titled “Using ICT to enhance marketing for small Agricultural producers” where it stated that “ICT solutions increase efficiency and improve competitive dynamics”

The world today has become so modern that almost everything is done online. Traditional marketing relied on the marketer moving from one place to another informing customers and potential customers of the existence of the product, but with the use of information and communication technologies (further – ICT), that can be done with the click of a button.

Setiowati, Hartoyo, Daryanto, & Arifin (2015) believed adopting ICT as a marketing tool (e-marketing) will lead to an increase in the organization's marketing potentials, and an increase in marketing capacity increases the performance of the business. Moornon and Slotegrant (1999) revealed that marketing has a positive effect on organizational

performance. Using ICT in business encourages collaboration and integration of businesses thus facilitating the entry of new products in the market. Setiowati, Hartoyo, Daryanto, & Arifin (2015) believes using ICT as a marketing tool has to will;

- Improves customer retention
- Reduce infractutural cost and
- Increases sales

Therefore, there is an increase need to include ICT in marketing. This study seeks to analyze the effects including ICT as a marketing strategy is going to have on the performances and growth of SMES.

2. PROBLEM STATEMENT

After a study carried out by El-Gohary (2010), where 365 articles were reviewed, he concluded that many gaps exist in e-marketing studies, especially the gap in examining the relationship between e-marketing and the performance of a business. Again, Alam and Noor (2009) noticed that most studies had been carried out on large organizations, thus creating a gap of knowledge in SMEs. ICT is fast evolving from an option in business to a necessity (Setiowati, Hartoyo, Daryanto, & Arifin (2015); Aderemi, Ojediran, Adegbite, & Olasanmi (2015); Constantinides, (2014); Qashou & Saleh, (2018)), still some businesses (especially SME) lack a clear view of the importance of ICT in their businesses, leading to a low adoption rate (Makipoa M. 2003). SME is the backbone of an economy, be it the sales of petty goods like shoes and bags to the sales of petrol or the sales of services such as hairdressing and teaching. Our everyday activities are centred on SME. The creation of awareness of the existence and importance of an SME product is a great way of contributing to its growth. ICT has taken over the minds of the population of today such that people cannot do without it. Most SMEs are still stuck in the traditional system of marketing, some because they don't know the importance of ICT, while others scare away from it because of its cost. ICT can be a great marketing strategy since most youths are clued to their phones and smart devices. The survival and growth of SME enterprise in modern days relies on them intergrading ICT into their activities, those that do not accept ICT cannot survive in today's developed economy, thus the need to highlight the importance of ICT to an SME's performance and growth. The survival of a company relies on its brand recognition, and the best way to get your business recognized today is through technology. Thus ICT is no longer an option in business marketing but it is becoming a necessity.

3. RESEARCH OBJECTIVE

ICT is designed to make life easier. This research has as main aim to understand the effects of integrating ICT into marketing on the performance of SMEs. Research carried out by Tsotsou & Vlachopoulou, (2011), Wu et al, (2003) and Brodie et al, (2011) show that e-marketing has a positive effect on performance. The question this study seeks to answer is "what are those effects?" It has the following objectives.

3.1. MAIN OBJECTIVE

To ascertain the impact of ICT as a marketing strategy has on SME's performance

3.2. SPECIFIC OBJECTIVES

- To ascertain the impact SME have on the profit by using ICT as a marketing strategy
- Enlighten today's entrepreneurs on the importance of incorporating ICT into their businesses
- To discover other relative effects of e-marketing on SME

4. RESEARCH QUESTIONS

- What effects does e-marketing have on the return of SMEs?
- Other than return, what other benefits does E-marketing have on SMEs ?

5. SCOPE OF THE STUDY

This study is applicable just to SMEs irrespective of their location in the world, be it developing or developed country. The study however pays emphasis on how ICT can affect the performance of a business if it is used as a marketing strategy. ICT has a variety of applications in a company, but this study will how ever be looking at its effects if it is applied as a marketing tool.

6. METHODOLOGY

The main characteristic of systematic literature reviews is that it follows a well laid down procedure that can be followed by another research and produce an identical result. Fink's (2005) definition of systematic literature review as reviewed by Okoli & Schabram (2010) highlighted the following terms: methodological approach, explicit, comprehensive and reproducible. The methodology used here was adopted and amended from Okoli & Schabram's (2010) model of carrying out a systematic literature review. Where instead of the 8 steps, this research follows 6 steps; searching the literature, practical screening, quality appraisal, analysis of findings, data extraction and writing the review. It can be graphically represented below.

Figure 1: A systematic guide to literature review development

Source: Okoli & Schabram (2010)

6.1. INCLUSION/EXCLUSION CRITERIA

For the purpose of objectivity and content validity, not all or any article searched was analysed in the study. The study followed some strict inclusions criteria before it was reviewed. Those criteria are as follows

- Only articles published between 2010- 2019 were considered. This is because a lot of literature has been reviewed in the last decade (2000-2010) by authors like Zott (2001), DTI (2010), Palialis (2007) and Gatautis (2008)
- Only Full-text articles were included
- Review articles, conference papers, journal articles, Encyclopedia, book chapters, reports and website articles were selected
- Research articles from all parts of the world were included
- Only articles are written in English
- All articles that doesn't fill the above mentions criteria were eliminated
- Gray literature was excluded.

6.2. SEARCHING THE LITERATURE

Due to the framework of a systematic literature review, primary data is not sourced nor analyzed (Okoli & Schabram, 2010). All data reviewed was sourced from secondary sources, precisely from the internet. The following databases were searched

- Science Direct
- Semantic Scholar
- Google Scholar

Google scholar is one of the biggest science databases with thousands of articles; both open access and close access. Alongside that, Science Direct and Semantic scholar were also used for the purpose of content validity.

The following keywords were searched on the above mentioned databases; ICT, Marketing, Performance as follows;

- ICT and Marketing and Performance and SME
- ICT and Marketing and Performance or SME
- ICT and/or Performance
- ICT and Marketing
- ICT and SME

6.3. PRACTICAL SCREENING

Searching the above mention databases will produce thousands of results. It is practically impossible to review all the articles searched for reasons that; there are too many, some are not directly related to the subject and others don't fall within the scope. To ensure that all articles were chosen to fall within the selection criteria, the following steps were taken

- For the criteria of years, the researcher used advance search. Advance search is a setting found in the above mention 3 data bases where you can choose criteria such as the years you wish to be included or excluded and the article type. The research chose the year 2010-2019. All articles are shown where published with the years 2010-2019.
- After the search has been done, and results shown, the researcher then read the topics of all the articles to choosing just those whose topic that fall within the scope of study and were written in English.

Some of the articles were not open access and due to financial limitations, the researcher could not download all the articles related to the topic, but rather downloaded all articles that filled the inclusion criteria and was open access. However, an article not being open access is not an exclusion criterion.

6.4. QUALITY APPRAISAL

This is the next stage after the practical selection. At this stage, the articles downloaded from the practical screening go through further screening to ensure that the quality of the articles meets standards of qualified research. The quality appraisal was carried out thus;

- The abstracts of the articles were read to insure that it falls within the scope of study and has something to contribute to the study.
- A deep further review of the articles was done, where the full text was read to verify its authenticity and ensure that the article was not in duplicates. Some articles found in Google scholar where also found in Science direct or semantic scholars.
- The methodology was also examined. Even though this research does not exclude articles based on methodology, however articles whose methodology is not clearly stated or not stated at all were excluded.

All articles that pass the quality appraisal stage are analyzed below based on their data or publication, databases sourced, country of origin and.

6.5. DATA EXTRACTION

This stage comes after the practical screening and quality appraisal stage has been completed. Articles considered for this stage must have passed through the above mentions stages. Here the articles are reviewed and information is systematically extracted to be used to draw a conclusion. After the quality appraisal, with the question in the back of

the researcher's head, he carefully read the final articles. Any articles that answer the research question or contribute to the drawing of conclusion on the study was written in a book specially designed for that purpose. Each article became on a new page and contended all relevant information for synthesis.

6.6. SYNTHESIS OF STUDIES

This is a very vital stage in a systematic literature review as it produces the conclusion. There exist several syntheses such as; qualitative synthesis of qualitative research, qualitative synthesis of quantitative research and quantitative synthesis of qualitative or quantitative research (Meta-analysis). This work will be using the meta-analysis method where all the research will be quantitatively analysed based on the variable to be ascertained in the literature review. From those variables, the research will come out with the results of this study and draw a conclusion

6.7. ANALYSIS OF FINDINGS

Data collected and analyzed in this study is solely secondary data consisting of published articles written by authors from the year 2010 to 2019. The findings here are the various different articles that pass the practical screening and quality appraisal. The analysis will be done according to Database, countries, date of Publication.

6.7.1. Analysis by Database

The researcher used the keywords mentioned in 6.2 to search for articles from the databases as mentioned above. Due to the advanced nature for the databases, some inclusion criteria such as the years included (2010-2019) and the type of articles (Review articles, conference papers, journal articles, Encyclopedia, book chapters) can be pre-set before the search is carried out, therefore the total number of articles listed below are after the two aforementioned criteria have been taken into consideration. After this stage, only articles that were open access considered, and amongst them only those directly related to the topic went through the quality appraisal stage. This is represented in the figure below.

Figure 2

Source: Author

6.7.2. Analysis by Date of publication.

All articles that pass the quality appraisal stage were used in the review stage. A total of 24 articles were reviewed, which were published from the year 2010 to 2019. This can be graphically represented below.

Figure 3

6.7.3. Analysis by Country

The articles reviewed came from a variety of countries ranging from African to European countries. These articles are represented below based on the country of publication

Figure 4

All the above information can be summarized in the table below.

Table 1

Citation	Material type	Synthesis type	Source of Data					
USAID (2013)	Report	Qualitative	Interview	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
Setiowati R. et al (2015),	Journal Paper	Quantitative	Questionnaire	☐	☐	☐	☐	
Matei A. and Savulescu C., (2012).	Journal Paper	Qualitative	Review of literature	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
Aderemi H. O. et al (2015)	Journal Paper	Mixed	Questionnaire and interview	☐	☐	☐		
Tadesse G. and Bahiigwa G., (2015)	Journal Paper	Mixed	Questionnaire and interview	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
Consoli D., (2012)	Journal Paper	Qualitative	Review of literature	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
Tiago M. T. and Tiago F., (2012).	Conference Paper	Quantitative	Questionnaire	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐

Source: Author	Tarutè A. and Gatautis R., (2014)	Journal Paper	Qualitative	Review of literature	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
	Constantinides E., (2014)	Journal Paper	Qualitative	Review of literature	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
	Dahnil M. I. et al (2014)	Journal Paper	Qualitative	Review of literature	☐	☐	☐	☐	
	Skudiene V. et al (2015)	Conference Paper	Qualitative	Review of literature	☐	☐	☐		☐
	Ciamiene R. and Stankeviciute G., (2015)	Conference Paper	Qualitative	Review of literature	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
	Rahman N. A. et al (2015)	Journal Paper	Qualitative	Review of literature	☐	☐	☐		
	Behera B. S. et al (2015).	Conference Paper	Qualitative	Case Study	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
	Jayaram D. et al (2015)	Journal Paper	Qualitative	Case Study	☐	☐	☐		
	Qashou A. and Saleh Y. (2018)	Journal Paper	Quantitative	Questionnaire	☐	☐	☐	☐	
	Nyaga E. K. (2012)	Journal Paper	Quantitative	Questionnaire	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
	El-Gohary H. (2010)	Journal Paper	Qualitative	Review of literature	☐	☐	☐	☐	
	Mochoge O. C. (2014).	Journal Paper	Quantitative	Questionnaire	☐	☐	☐		
	Mazurek G. (2012).	Journal Paper	Qualitative	Case Study	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
	Reenen J. V. et al (2010).	Report	-	-	☐	☐	☐	☐	
	Andreopoulou, Z. et al (2014)	Journal Paper	Qualitative	Case Study	☐	☐	☐	☐	
	Išoraitė, M. 2014	Journal Paper	Qualitative	Review of literature	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
Kiveu, M. and Ofafa, G. (2013)	Journal Paper	Qualitative	Review of literature	☐	☐	☐			

7. WRITING THE REVIEW

ICT as a marketing technique has many names; internet marketing, e-marketing, digital marketing, online marketing and interactive marketing (Tiago M. and Tiago F 2012). Smith and Chaffey (2005) defined e-marketing as “achieving marketing objectives by applying digital technology”. Strauss and Frost (2001) defined it as “the use of electronic data and application for planning and executing the conception, distribution and pricing of ideas, goods and services to create exchanges that satisfy individual and organizational goals”

7.1. OPERATIONALISATION OF VARIABLES

The performance of a business can be measured using indicators like; return and growth. The main objective of a business is to make a profit, which makes return the primary indication of this study.

Our question one is based on the analysis of the effects e-marketing has on SME’s return. As earlier established, e-marketing has a positive effect on return, so this study isn’t limited to determining if it is a positive or negative effect but it goes further to analyse those effects that most authors have talked about. There exist two major ways to increase return;

- Maximize revenue
- Minimize cost

Murtaga A. (2008) believed that ICT in an organization leads to cost reduction, thereby increasing return. Aderemi et al (2015) believed sales are one of the basics for the assessment of the company’s performance as it increases its profit. These gave birth to question 1, where the research review all the articles that pass the quality appraisal stage looking for articles that support the fact that using ICT as a marketing strategy increases the company’s return either by increases sale(effectiveness) or by reducing cost (efficiency) or through both

Question 2, tries to come out with other positive effects E-marketing has on the performance of a company other than increase return. Even though Reenen J. et al (2010) did not research on the effects of ICT as a marketing strategy, he however believed ICT has a direct relationship to productivity and gives the organization a comparative advantage such as customer’s satisfaction, gain market coverage and brand loyalty creation, which the author believed if used as a marketing strategy could have such effect. Kiveu M. and Ofafa G. (2013) believed one of the main problems faced by SMES is low market access and competitiveness. However believed using ICT as a

marketing strategy can solve this problem. Therefore, question 2 will be based on reviewing the articles to see the authors who believe that productivity and/or competitive advantage is an after effect of using e-marketing.

7.2. PRESENTATION OF RESULTS

Table 2: Presentation of result

Source: Author

Citation	Synthesis	Question 1		Question 2	
		Max Sales	Min Cost	Productivity	Comparative advantage
USAID (2013)	■			√	√
Matei A. and Savulescu C., (2012).	■	√	√	√	√
Tadesse G. and Bahiigwa G., (2015)	■		√		
Consoli D., (2012)	■	√	√	√	√
Tiago M. T. and Tiago F., (2012).	■		√		√
Tarutè A. and Gatautis R., (2014)	■			√	√
Constantinides E., (2014)	■		√		√
Skudiene V. et al (2015)	■				√
Ciamiene R. and Stankeviciute G., (2015)	■	√	√		√
Behera B. S. et al (2015).	■		√		√
Nyaga E. K. (2012)	■				√
Mazurek G. (2012).	■				√
Išoraitė, M. 2014	■		√		√

From the above table, a total of 13 papers were synthesized, of those 13, 3 of them mentioned that using ICT as a marketing strategy has a direct effect on sales, of the 13, 7 mentioned that e-marketing would reduce the cost of the organization. Also, based on question2, out of 13 articles, 4 mentioned productivity as an effect of using e-marketing and of the 13, 12 mentions comparative advantage as another effect of using e-marketing.

7.3. CONCLUSION

This research aimed to enlighten the owners of SMEs on the effects ICT has on the performance of SMEs if being used as a marketing strategy. From the result shown above, it can be seen that e-marketing will increase the sales of the company and also reduce its cost. However, the major effect of e-marketing on returns is the reduction of cost as compared to an increase in sales

Also, it can be seen that e-marketing will increase the growth of SMEs by increasing its productivity, since it has the market to supply the products. The major effect on growth by e-market as seen in the result is comparative advantage, where out of 13 articles, 12 talked of comparative advantage.

However, irrespective of the positive effects ICT in general and e-marketing in particular have on SMEs, some SMEs are reluctant to embrace ICT. Setiowati R. et al (2015) believed it is a result of high installation costs and lack of adequate knowledge. On this note, the author suggests that the government should intervene and subsidize the cost of the installation of e-marketing tools so as to help SMEs cope with technological changes.

7.4. Recommendation for further study

- Carry out this study on a quantitative approach

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